

Standardising Clinical Outcome measures in
Routinely-collected Electronic healthcare
systems data

SCORE-CVD – Initial Report

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1. Background

The use of routinely-collected healthcare data (also known as electronic health records) in randomised clinical trials offers the potential to deliver more efficient and cost-effective trials. However, it also presents challenges, with a very small proportion (~3%) of clinical trials estimated to be using this data.

The Data-Enabled Trials area within the BHF Data Science Centre (BHF DSC) would like to make it easier for researchers and clinicians to safely and securely access electronic health records to support, or replace data that is collected just for a clinical trial. We want to facilitate this transformation in the way clinical trials can be done.

In 2021, BHF DSC completed a survey of UK Clinical Trials Units to explore the use of routinely-collected health records (also referred to as electronic health records (Healthcare systems datasets) or healthcare systems data (HSD)) in trials, (1) building on previous surveys by HDR UK (2). The responses highlighted clear challenges to the access and use of this data (<https://zenodo.org/record/5079178>).

Following this, BHF DSC invited the broader cardiovascular community to participate in a workshop along with members of National Cardiac Surgery Clinical Trials Initiative. During those workshops, the existing challenges were discussed with initiatives identified for the BHF Data Science Centre to support the trials community. These were: (1) 'Provide guidance', (2) 'Develop best practice', (3) 'Standardise clinical outcome measures for CVD trials using electronic health records', (4) 'Use leverage to improve processes' and (5) develop driver projects.

In this project, Standardising Clinical Outcome measures in Routinely-collected Electronic healthcare systems data (SCORE-CVD), we are collaborating with the Computable Phenotypes area within the BHF DSC.

A computable phenotype is a way of finding out if a person has a specific characteristic or disease (within trials we commonly refer to this as an outcome) by analysing information from electronic health records (EHRs). Phenotyping algorithms are computable instructions that use the information contained within healthcare systems datasets to identify people with, or who have experienced, a specific clinical event/disease or characteristic.

The SCORE-CVD project aims to define community-agreed best practices for the derivation, format, and storage of phenotyping algorithms using Electronic Health Records (healthcare systems datasets [HSD]) for commonly used clinical trial outcome measures.

2. Aims

- Define best practices (community-agreed) for derivation, format & storage of phenotyping algorithms using HSD for commonly-used outcome measures.
- Identify phenotyping algorithms already used to successfully define outcome measures for trials.
- Where needed, develop new phenotyping algorithms to derive outcome measures commonly used in cardiovascular clinical trials using best practices.

3. Planning

The SCORE-CVD project is led by Prof Matt Sydes (BHF Data Science Centre Associate Director for Data-enabled Trials) and Sarah Lessels (BHF DSC project manager), supported by other members of BHF DSC, and delivered by working with a Steering Group and a number of outcome-specific 'Task and Finish' Groups focusing on the following areas:

- Phenotyping algorithm requirements
- Myocardial Infarction
- Stroke
- Major Bleeding
- Heart failure
- Death/Mortality

This report covers findings from the initial round of workshops from all groups and details plans for the next steps for SCORE-CVD.

Each workshop was based on a series of questions and slides designed to match the aims of the session. Attendees were split into discussion groups to consider each of the workshop aims and then group discussions were held after each break out.

4. Workshops - Phenotyping algorithm requirements

4.1 Workshop aims

- To establish what the cardiovascular clinical trials community need to use standard outcomes from healthcare systems data (using phenotyping algorithms)

Discussion groups considered the following areas:

- Finding and identifying phenotyping algorithms
- How to know if a phenotyping algorithm meets the needs of the trial team
- Information needed to use and apply the phenotyping algorithms
- Any other considerations the group wanted to add

Mural boards¹ were used to capture key points around each area during breakout sessions, followed by a group discussion.

4.2 Workshop organisation

Workshops were held on the 30-Jan-2023 and 02-Feb-2023. Attendees are listed in **Appendix 1**.

4.3 Key Discussion topics

The group felt that in order for a phenotyping algorithm to be selected and used by the clinical trials community they would need to have confidence that a clinical review of the algorithm had been completed. As clinical definitions of disease and recording patterns change over time, regular clinical review of algorithms would be important to allow a set of standard phenotyping algorithms to be developed, and a frequency and method of review should be agreed. The SCORE-CVD group could form the basis of a repeat review panel, this review process would lead on to endorsement.

Endorsement of phenotyping algorithms was discussed and the group felt that endorsement from a recognised society, national body and the SCORE-CVD group would be helpful. This endorsement could be highlighted via naming convention and/or within the outcome information. It was also felt to be important to allow the community to select a phenotyping algorithm and have confidence in it. The group also felt that sharing this work with international collaborators would be beneficial.

The title and naming convention for phenotyping algorithms was highlighted; it needs to be clear which dataset and medical ontology are being used. Information layering was also considered: first and importantly, the group felt that a plain English/lay summary should precede a more technical description, which would outline methods and logic, followed by a final layer with the coding instructions and options for different languages i.e., R, Stata, Python.

When discussing how to use the phenotyping algorithms, the group felt it was key to reference instructions on how to prepare and curate the source EHR data in a standard way to ensure fair comparison, description of curation methods would allow cross-trial comparison. It would also be useful to have clear instructions for how to apply the same phenotyping algorithm on data from different UK nations, and possibly internationally.

Information on how the phenotyping algorithm had been validated (e.g., manual review of clinical notes by clinicians, comparison against source data or registry data and adjudication) would also be

¹ <https://www.mural.co/>

important to include with the phenotype. In addition, information on the performance of the algorithm would support usage.

The developed algorithms would be published in order to promote the use of standardised outcome measures. Standards for publications were also discussed, with the important principle trial teams should start their chosen algorithm before trials analyses.

4.4 Discussion area findings

4.4.1 Finding/identifying Phenotyping algorithms

- Phenotypes should be clearly named and searchable
- Phenotype purpose or outcome of interest (e.g., hospitalisations for indication or time-to-event)
- Publication reference and DOI of publication
- Cross-maps to other ontologies e.g. MeSH, SNOMED CT, MONDO etc
- Reference to clinical trials (ISRCTN or EuDRACT) from which the phenotype was developed and to which it has been applied
- Ontology term(s) to represent phenotype (support synonyms and child terms)

4.4.2 Knowing if a phenotyping algorithm meets your needs

- Details of validation of the phenotyping algorithm including type of validation and outcome i.e. validation utilising trial source data
- Results from validation including sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values
- Comment/feedback section to allow input if a phenotype is not suitable for a given purpose
- Endorsement, date of review for clinical input (method to manage addition of new medical ontology terms/clinical practice) and name of endorsing organisation
- Regulatory approvals (if granted) and approval committee details
- Population inclusion/exclusion criteria (if applicable)
- Datasets the relevant codes can be located in with link to information on their coverage across the UK
- Flag phenotypes that can be used internationally (if coded appropriately)

4.4.3 How to use/apply a phenotyping algorithm

- Flowchart to describe rules based algorithm
- Link to source code
- Dataset-specific implementation details i.e. Diagnosis code position (primary vs any) in administrative hospitalization records or mortality data or defining episodes and spells.

5. Mortality

5.1 Workshop aims

- Discuss the choice between all-cause mortality and cardiovascular death as trial and study outcome measure
- Discuss what is included in the definition of cardiovascular death and what computable phenotypes may need to be defined
- Review and discuss some existing phenotypes for cardiovascular death

5.2 Workshop organisation

The mortality workshop was held on 01-Mar-2023. Members of the cardiovascular clinical trials community and the BHF DSC attended (see **Appendix 1**).

5.3 Key Discussion topics

5.3.1 Discuss choice between all-cause mortality and cardiovascular death as outcome measure

All three discussion groups agreed that all-cause mortality is a binary outcome measure and likely to be well recorded within UK health records. All-cause mortality may also be more likely to be used in trials using electronic health records due to issues with defining cardiovascular death.

Non-cancer death was put forward as an alternative outcome measure that may also be helpful to define.

Prior to the group session, the group had been sent a publication (3) '2017 Cardiovascular and Stroke Endpoint Definitions for Clinical Trials' which includes a definition of cardiovascular death. The definitions were highlighted as being well accepted within the community but a clear focus was required to translate these definitions into what is possible with EHR data both currently and in the future.

The groups agreed that adjudication committees are still required for many trials; however the roles of these committees may be changing. Adjudication could move from traditional adjudication to reduced event adjudication or adjudication committees could be involved in evaluation of methods/validation for using healthcare systems datasets. There was disagreement on the extent to which clinical review would remain critical.

5.3.2 Discuss what is included within cardiovascular death and what computable phenotypes may need to be defined

The groups agreed that the definition of cardiovascular death within '2017 Cardiovascular and Stroke Outcome measure Definitions for Clinical Trials' is widely accepted, however the group identified some components which may require further discussion: Sudden cardiac death was felt to incorporate all sudden deaths not all of which may be cardiovascular, and some indications listed under cardiovascular haemorrhage may not be cardiovascular and as such would not fit within the list. It was felt that some definitions such as those under stroke would make it easier to ascribe cardiovascular death whereas it may be more difficult with the MI description which incorporates any cardiovascular death within 30 days of an MI. The temporal relationship between MI and cardiovascular death may be more important than with other cardiovascular causes of death to ensure confidence in the cause of death. The group observed that the closer a death was to a defined cardiovascular event the easier it is to assign cause of death. This relationship would be important to capture when developing an CVD death algorithm. For example, it was suggested that

an algorithm for cardiovascular death may include deaths preceded by cardiovascular codes such as MI or stroke within the 30 days prior to death.

Any cardiovascular death listed in position 1a on the death certificate was felt to be reliable if the patient died in hospital. There was some discussion about whether the first three positions could be used.

(Form prescribed by Registration of Births and Deaths Regulations 1987)

MEDICAL CERTIFICATE OF CAUSE OF DEATH
For use only by a Registered Medical Practitioner WHO HAS BEEN IN ATTENDANCE during the deceased's last illness, and to be delivered by him forthwith to the Registrar of Births and Deaths.

No. of Death Entry

Name of deceased.....

Date of death as stated to me day of..... Age as stated to me

Place of death.....

Last seen alive by me day of.....

1 The certified cause of death takes account of information obtained from post-mortem. }
 2 Information from post-mortem may be available later }
 3 Post mortem not being held. }
 4 I have reported this death to the Coroner for further action. }

Please print appropriate digit, and letter

a Seen after death by me.
 b Seen after death by another medical practitioner but not by me
 c Not seen after death by a medical practitioner.

(See overleaf)

CAUSE OF DEATH
The condition thought to be the 'Underlying Cause of Death' should appear on the line completed line of Part I.

I (a) Disease or condition directly leading to death?

(b) Other disease or condition, if any, leading to: I(a)

(c) Other disease or condition, if any, leading to: I(b)

II Other significant conditions CONTRIBUTING TO THE DEATH but not related to the disease or condition causing it

These particulars not to be entered in death register
Approximate interval between onset and death

Illustration 1: Specimen Death Certificate

The group also discussed the contribution of death to MACE (Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events) as a composite outcome measure and agreed that cardiovascular outcome definitions varied when being used as part of a composite outcome. However, it was also agreed that MACE definitions varied widely and a standardised version using healthcare systems datasets would be very useful.

There were no existing phenotypes for cardiovascular death listed on the HDRUK Phenotype library for discussion, again highlighting the need for this piece of work to be developed.

5.4 Key delivery points

- Develop algorithm for cardiovascular death, including both the code list and the “best practice” metadata required
- Algorithm for non-cancer death may be useful
- A healthcare systems data version of MACE would be beneficial although this is also relevant to the areas under discussion in other Task and Finish groups

6. Myocardial Infarction (MI)

6.1 Workshop aims

- To review and consider existing MI Computable Phenotypes from the HDR Phenotype Library
- To discuss known MI Computable Phenotypes not yet in phenotyping libraries
- To consider any priority gaps for MI outcome measures which require new computable phenotypes

6.2 Workshop organisation

The myocardial infarction workshop was held on 10-Feb-2023, and information on attendees can be found in Appendix 1.

6.3 Discussion topics

6.3.1. To review and consider existing MI Computable Phenotypes from phenotyping libraries

The initial discussion asked participants to review a Myocardial Infarction phenotype from the HDRUK Phenotyping library (PH988) and discuss if they could use this in a trial. The phenotype contains both secondary and primary care codes. The group felt that they would be more likely to rely on ICD-10 codes in secondary care, since use of primary care data may add sensitivity but it was highlighted that there may be a compromise in accuracy and positive predictive value.

The group also discussed and agreed that the data within secondary care coding could not yet be used to sub classify between Type 1 and Type 2 MI's.

From the secondary codes available the group felt strongly that key ICD-10 codes of interest were:

I21 – Acute Myocardial Infarction

I22 – Subsequent Myocardial Infarction

The phenotype used during the discussion also contained additional codes: Dressler's syndrome and Old Myocardial Infarction. The group agreed that while it depended on the research being conducted they would be unlikely to incorporate these codes into a standard MI definition for a trial.

6.3.2 To discuss known MI Computable Phenotypes not yet in phenotyping libraries

The group highlighted that not all researchers share and upload phenotypes into libraries and there is not a standard resource recognised by clinical triallists. The group identified that I21 and I22 are the key ICD-10 terms; however it is the rules for applying these terms that can cause the difficulties for researchers with few good examples of how these are dealt with. The RIPCORD2 Trial (4) was referenced as an example where the supplemental material does clearly include the determination of clinical events. The group discussed that clear guidelines to interpret initial and subsequent MI's during a follow up period may be required, depending on the primary and secondary outcome measures of a trial. Algorithms for subsequent MI's may look at discharge dates and then use the first I21 code introduced after the discharge; however this is not perfect for two reasons: it will not identify a recurrent MI occurring within the same admission as the index event; and it will not take into account that a previous MI may be coded in a subsequent admission without there having been a new (recurrent) MI.

It was also highlighted the ONS data for cause of death coding may be important to identify possible events, although this would depend on the code position – for example the first position may be used to ascertain cardiovascular death. It was noted that this would be explored further in the planned mortality session.

A clear method for grouping episodes/spells would also be important – it was confirmed that it was possible to manage this grouping both within NHS England Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) data, Public Health Scotland data and in PEDW for Wales although episodes and spells have to be grouped and handled differently in Scotland vs England and Wales.

6.3.3 Consider any priority gaps for MI outcome measures which require new computable phenotypes

The group discussed and reiterated that sub-classification of MI would not currently be achieved with current national electronic health records. There was also discussion about whether it would be useful to define procedural MI, due to the discordance in how this is recorded; again it was felt that that the priority should be to define initial and recurrent MI phenotypes.

Other common outcome measures such as reduction in infarct size could not be evaluated using electronic health records. A hybrid approach may therefore be required for some clinical trials, moving forward with phenotyping algorithms which are well-defined and validated being suitable for some elements of clinical trials and traditional clinical trial source data to complement this for other outcome measures.

6.4 Key delivery points

- Development of ‘initial Myocardial Infarction’ algorithm, including both the code list and the “best practice” metadata required
- Development of algorithm to count ‘all Myocardial Infarction’ events
- Development of ‘recurrent Myocardial Infarction’ algorithm
- Define/share method and guidance for grouping episodes/spells in hospitals

7. Heart Failure

7.1 Workshop aims

- Discuss Phenotypes (outcome measures) of interest for Heart Failure
- Review existing examples from the HDR Phenotype Library
- Discuss example primary outcome measures from existing trials

7.2 Workshop organisation

The heart failure workshop was held on 10-Mar-2023, and a list of attendees can be found in **Appendix 1**.

7.3 Discussion topics

7.3.1 Discuss Phenotypes (outcome measures) of interest for Heart Failure

The group highlighted that heart failure is one of the more difficult diagnoses to identify using healthcare systems datasets. In addition, clinical definitions in this area are frequently changing, and the clinical coding systems are not updated as frequently.

Heart failure classification can be by anatomy, aetiology or ejection fraction. It was felt that anatomical and aetiological subtypes are covered within ICD-10 coding, but not ejection fraction. The group felt it may be useful to consider what possible ways ejection fraction could be extracted in future for better characterisation. A standard definition for heart failure hospitalisation was discussed and it was felt that this would be helpful. It was felt that heart failure in primary position may not always reflect accurately the reason for hospitalisation.

The groups all felt that NYHA Classification is very helpful in identifying worsening heart failure; however, this is not recorded in secondary care data and is not reliably recorded in primary care data.

Primary care data was felt to be useful. For example, some algorithms including primary care codes have been developed by Bristol Clinical Trials Unit but not yet validated. Prescribing data were recognised to be well recorded in primary care (and could be supplemented by linkage to medication dispensing data) and may be very helpful when ejection fraction data are not complete. It was agreed that outcome measures such as heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) are particularly complicated and challenging to identify with healthcare systems datasets.(5)

Other relevant outcome measures in development were highlighted such as cumulative days in hospital, cumulative days alive outside hospital and numbers of outpatient appointments, all of which should be achievable using healthcare systems datasets.

7.3.2 Review existing examples from Phenotype Library

The group discussed an existing phenotype from the HDR UK Phenotype Library (PH182) and compared this against terms used within the National Heart Failure Audit (NHFA).

Initial discussion revolved around whether ICD-10 terms for ischaemic cardiomyopathy and dilated cardiomyopathy represented definite heart failure. Some members of the group felt that heart failure was an umbrella term and that all of the codes listed should be incorporated. The NHFA codes exclude I13 (HF due to hypertension with renal disease) and I97.1 (following cardiac surgery or due to presence of cardiac prosthesis). The reason for these exclusions is unknown and the group felt that these codes would be included within a heart failure definition.

7.3.3 Discuss example primary outcome measures from existing trials

The groups were presented with two existing clinical trials with the primary outcome measures below and asked to consider if healthcare systems datasets could be utilised to evaluate primary outcome measures:

1. Primary Outcome Measure: Incidence rate for total heart failure (HF) hospitalizations or cardiovascular (CV) death
<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02901184>
2. Primary Outcome Measures: Incidence of Heart Failure
<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT05043610>

When discussing the incidence rate of total heart failure hospitalisations the group felt that they would need to cast a wide net to capture all potentially relevant events i.e. increasing the sample size to manage false positives. It was also identified that heart failure hospitalisation may not be the best choice of outcome measure and all-cause hospitalisation may be better as this is important to the patient and this would capture the wide range of symptoms that patients with heart failure may be admitted with, e.g. kidney issues, maybe even stroke. The need for validation of heart failure outcome measures was reiterated in this discussion.

For the second outcome measure, the sample size was much smaller (240 patients) and the group agreed this could not be achieved with HES data alone. Evaluation of the primary outcome would be done within clinic or an additional suggestion was made that GP data could be utilised along with prescribing data. There may be existing algorithms in place using such data; however, identification and validation of algorithms is needed.

7.4 Key delivery points

- Development of an algorithm to capture all heart failure events, including both the code list and the “best practice” metadata required
- Development of a heart failure-hospitalisation algorithm would be helpful. Additional work is needed to define what is classed as a HF hospitalisation
- Future development of an all-cause hospitalisation algorithm to capture wide range of HF-relevant symptoms
- Future consideration to identify data that may be used to develop algorithms to characterise ejection fraction status

8. Major Bleeding

8.1 Workshop aims

- Identify why major/significant bleeding is important as an outcome measure within clinical trials
- Discuss the types of bleeding that should be captured
- Review and discuss some existing code lists against bleeding

8.2 Workshop organisation

The major bleeding workshop was held on 17-Feb-2023, and a list of attendees can be found in **Appendix 1**.

8.3 Discussion topics

8.3.1 Identify why major bleeding is important as an outcome measure for clinical trials

The group discussed major bleeding outcome measures for trials, with the conclusion that major or significant bleeding is important across the spectrum of cardiovascular disease and interventions, a number of key points were mentioned:

- Major bleeding is an important outcome measure for cardiovascular treatment and prevention trials, being highly relevant to consequences of prevention treatments such as anti-coagulants.
- Major/significant bleeding is important; however, minor bleeding can lead to change in treatment. Patients who have a minor bleed may stop receiving anti-thrombotic therapy which in turn could lead to ischaemic complications.
- Intracranial haemorrhage is a major bleeding event and well defined within electronic health records.
- Hospitalisation or prolonged hospitalisation with a diagnosis of bleeding may be a good way to identify major bleeding events.
- Peripheral arterial disease is one significant risk factor for major bleeding and may be important to consider in outcome measures.
- Gastro-intestinal bleeding – important to identify and can be linked. particularly to major bleeds after various cardiovascular procedures when patients are taking blood thinning medication.
- BARC (Bleeding Academic Research Consortium) criteria are commonly used and ISTH (International Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis) criteria were also referenced. These criteria were introduced as prior to this it was difficult to compare bleeding event rates between trials due to differences in definitions.

8.3.2 Discuss the types of bleeding that should be captured

The BARC criteria were used to discuss and identify some key data points that may be used when building new phenotyping algorithms.

- Hospitalisation for bleeding and extension of hospitalisation for bleeding could be considered significant bleeding events. It was also suggested that reasons for hospitalisation could be used as an exclusion criteria – i.e. where the bleed is not the primary reason for admission or the stay is <24hrs.

- Stopping medications such as DAPT could be useful to collect to identify significant bleeding – defining this as significant to the patient rather than matching the existing major bleed criteria.
- Transfusion records were discussed as these are included within some national registry data but transfusion data are not yet widely available and are not reliably captured in HES. It was highlighted that records for transfusion can be confusing – patients with anaemia would be a high risk for a major bleed and may be given pre-operative units. Whether this data would be useful is dependent on the structure of the dataset and its linkage to other data.
- Procedure records such as treatments for cardiac tamponade may be useful but this is also common for cancer patients. The group discussed if cancer patients would be likely to be ineligible for cardiovascular trials but this was felt not to be the case - cancer patients are at higher risk of major bleeding events and now likely to be included in cardiovascular trials. It was suggested that developing rules to look at cardiovascular procedure date +/- time period before cardiac tamponade would be a more successful way to identify such major bleeding cases.
- Intracranial haemorrhage is a major bleeding event and well defined. It was queried if this should be standalone phenotype however the group felt this was a rarer event and would fit in with an algorithm to define all major or significant bleeding. This would also depend on the trial, trials evaluating anti-thrombotic treatments may require a separately defined outcome for intracranial haemorrhage.
- Intraocular bleeds that compromise vision were discussed and group members mentioned this could be difficult to identify. The data is present within eye registries and possibly within primary care data but these episodes are likely to be managed as day-case procedures and so not readily identified through HES.
- Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG)-related bleeding is mentioned within BARC but this would be difficult to identify within EHR.
- When discussing fatal bleeding it was felt that bleeding codes present in positions 1a-c of the death certificate are likely to be accurate; however, it was also highlighted that bleeding as a cause of death may be under-recorded. Algorithms when being developed should consider the sequence of events that has potentially resulted in patient death – i.e., reason for admission, date/time of procedure, time of bleed.

8.3.3 Review and discuss some existing code lists against bleeding

The group considered some existing code lists (4)(6). There was some discussion around the approach as one study took a hybrid approach utilising ICD-10 codes to identify bleeding events, followed by interrogation of medical records. It was felt that this was useful but the current aim of the group was to move to method utilising only electronic health records.

Comments in relation to the secondary analysis (7) of the ASCEND trial highlighted that a looser definition of bleeding could lead to missed signals whilst a tighter definition adding in multiple factors led to a stronger treatment effect and whilst there may be some loss of events the data was more reliable, there needs to be some balance in the algorithm developed (8). The next stage of the process would involve testing scenarios possibly utilising simulated or de-identified data.

8.4 Key delivery points

- An algorithm/algorithms for major bleeding should be developed using criteria that are available within healthcare systems data, including both the code list and the “best practice” metadata required
- This may be an alternative to BARC, rather than an attempt to construct BARC from healthcare systems data which would not be achievable
- Adjudication has been important for bleeding-based outcome measures; in order to move away from this, validation of new algorithm will be important.

9. Stroke

9.1 Workshop aims

- Discuss stroke classification and requirements for phenotypes (clinical trial outcome measures)
- Review existing examples of stroke phenotypes from the Phenotype Library
- Consider data sources for phenotypes – primary & secondary care

9.2 Workshop organisation

The stroke workshop was held on 08-Mar-2023, and a list of attendees can be found in **Appendix 1**.

9.3 Discussion topics

9.3.1 Discuss Stroke classification and requirements for phenotypes (clinical trial outcome measures)

All groups felt that requirement for classification of stroke was dependent on the research question. For example, trials evaluating blood pressure treatments may only require 'all -stroke' whereas a trial evaluating lipid lowering, antithrombotic or several other drugs, may require sub classification.

Groups agreed that categories would include ischaemic and haemorrhagic stroke; however, unknown or unclassified stroke would also be required as a sub-classification. It was mentioned that if sub-classification was required then some trials have grouped unclassified strokes along with ischaemic strokes; however, this requires acceptance of a certain level of mis-classification.

Previous clinical classifications such as OCSF (Oxford Community Stroke Project) classification would not be helpful in creating algorithms as these are based on clinical symptoms and unlikely to be found within healthcare systems datasets.

Transient Ischaemic Strokes (TIAs) were discussed, as these are commonly included within clinical trial outcome measures, if TIAs are excluded from the trial outcome the justification within the protocols tends to focus on unreliable data. TIAs would only appear in HES data if severity required hospital admission and many would only be identified in GP records. The ASCEND trial experience was that TIA was the outcome measure most different in frequency of collection between trial forms and healthcare systems datasets, GP data was not used in this comparison which may explain the differential. In addition the way in which TIAs are recorded in GP data can vary – examples given were that in some cases a GP may record TIA on presentation of symptoms, others may not record a TIA until diagnosis is confirmed post referral. The group felt that recommendations for TIAs would be helpful.

Further sub-classification of stroke may be possible using brain imaging reporting data, currently only available in Scotland and Wales.

9.3.2 Review existing examples of Stroke phenotypes from the Phenotype Library

The group reviewed existing phenotypes within the phenotype library (PH56, PH1018, PH948, PH983 and PH948). Discussion confirmed that the ICD-10 codes for haemorrhagic stroke were accurate, and the group would utilise the ICD-10 codes within PH56 and PH1018 for ischaemic stroke with the exception of I69.3 (sequelae of cerebral infarction) as this is not linked to new stroke events. I64 – unspecified stroke, was also identified as required.

9.3.3 Consider data sources for phenotypes – primary & secondary care

The groups were presented with data from a study ‘Concordance in the recording of stroke across UK primary and secondary care datasets: a population-based cohort study’ (9). In a comparison of 75,674 stroke events only 40% of events were detectable in both CPRD and HES datasets.

The group discussed how this data may not show the sensitivity for stroke recording in either dataset; it was flagged that primary care data may have issues with re-recording of old diagnoses (although this can also happen within secondary care data). It was also highlighted again that there is not a one size fits all outcome measure for stroke, and that some trials may require time to first stroke. Stroke prevention trials may incorporate patients with history of stroke.

If utilising multiple data sources, it would be important to establish rules to manage disagreement between sources.

The group also highlighted that some patients with stroke, for example in nursing homes, may not be admitted to hospital. Use of GP records may allow researchers to find additional events not listed in HES; however, additional adjudication manually may be required to evaluate genuine events. It was also suggested that ONS death registration data can be utilised to capture events, for example with stroke listed as the primary cause of death.

It was also flagged that existing trial data has demonstrated that many strokes including ischaemic strokes, are not captured in HES due to patients being managed as outpatients, therefore the addition of outpatient data should be considered when developing these algorithms (9).

The power for any trial was also highlighted: one impact from a possible decision to capture only strokes that ended up in hospitalisation would mean fewer events but may mean the results are more targeted allowing a larger treatment effect to be sought.

9.4 Key delivery points

- Development of an all-stroke algorithm;, important to incorporate unclassified strokes within this. Guidance on grouping these types of stroke will be helpful.
- Development of a separate algorithm combining primary and secondary care data with rules on how to manage sources
- Separate algorithms for ischaemic and haemorrhagic stroke could also be included.
- These algorithms should include both the code list and the “best practice” metadata required

10. Common Requirements

The following elements were considered to be required across all diagnoses:

- ***Clinical Validation and endorsement***

Across all workshops there was a clear need for clinical evaluation of phenotyping algorithms and agreed endorsement. Agreement of review on a regular basis would allow support for researchers to use algorithms being recommended, this may also support regulatory approval and publication.

- ***Naming conventions***

Identified within the phenotyping requirements session, the need for this was emphasised across sessions. Clear labelling to allow researchers to identify appropriately endorsed and validated algorithms.

- ***Means to display algorithm 'rules'***

The groups discussed suitable codes during all sessions but there is also the need to capture the complexity of the algorithm rules to combine the codes. A mechanism is needed to display the rules in plain English to allow all members of the trial team to identify algorithms appropriate to their trial with confidence.

- ***Clear Validation***

Information to show that the algorithm has been validated and the method which has been used for validation, along with information derived from the validation for example Sensitivity, specificity Positive and negative predictive values. The trials community felt that the validation gold standard would be to work with data from existing trial datasets with adjudicated outcome measures.

11. Prioritised Phenotype List

Mortality

- Cardiovascular death
- Non-cancer death
- Standard MACE (non-fatal stroke, non-fatal myocardial infarction, or cardiovascular death)

Myocardial Infarction

- Initial Myocardial Infarction
- All Myocardial Infarction
- Recurrent Myocardial Infarction

Heart Failure

- Heart Failure
- Heart Failure hospitalisation
- All-cause hospitalisation – with criteria to identify HF symptoms

Major Bleeding

- Clinically-significant Bleeding – appropriate naming convention to be discussed, as per major bleeding discussion this would not recreate clinical bleeding outcome measures such as BARC

Stroke

- All stroke – secondary care only
- All stroke – secondary & primary care/incorporate TIAs
- Ischaemic Stroke
- Haemorrhagic Stroke
- Recurrent stroke

12. Proposed delivery plan

13. References

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Abbreviations: Phenotyping Requirements (PR) Heart Failure (HF) Death/Mortality (DM) Stroke (S)
Major Bleeding (MB) Myocardial Infarction (MI)

Appendix 2 –Phenotypes referenced during workshops

PH182 – Heart Failure:

<https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/PH182/version/364/detail/>

PH988 – Acute Myocardial Infarction:

<https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/PH988/version/2166/detail/>

PH56 - Ischaemic Stroke: <https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/?search=PH56>

PH1018 – Stroke: <https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/?search=PH1018>

PH948 – Stroke: <https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/?search=PH948>

PH983 – Stroke: <https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/?search=PH983>